

TRAIL-AND-ERROR ALGORITHM FOR ALGEBRAIC FUZZY NEURAL NETWORKS USING TRIANGULAR FUZZY NUMBERS

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ABSTRACT

An architecture of fuzzy neural network with triangular fuzzy weights (usually non-symmetric), and an adapted trail-and-error learning algorithm are presented. The network is able to map a vector of triangular fuzzy numbers into any other vector of triangular fuzzy numbers.

KEYWORDS: fuzzy neural networks, triangular fuzzy weights, vector of fuzzy numbers, trail-and-error algorithm.

INTRODUCTION

Various approaches of fuzzification of the neural networks have been proposed [1]. Some of them use fuzzy logic, implementing *if-then rules*, others use arithmetic fuzzy numbers [1-2].

A recent class of neuro-fuzzy systems is based on neural network topology and fuzzy algebraic systems [1]. Two approaches of arithmetic fuzzy neural network have been proposed in [2,3] and respectively in [4].

Ishibuchi [2,3] proposed an architecture of multilayer feedforward algebraic neural network for fuzzy input vectors. The output of this fuzzy neural network is a vector of fuzzy numbers. The input-output relations in this fuzzy neural network, using max/min operators, are defined by the extension principle of Zadeh. In these papers, the authors used only symmetric triangular fuzzy numbers [2,3]. A cost function for the level sets (a-cuts) of fuzzy outputs and fuzzy target is defined. The fuzzy output from each unit in the fuzzy neural network is computed for level sets of fuzzy inputs, fuzzy weights and fuzzy biases. The learning algorithm, based on the cost function, uses a gradient descent method. A heuristic method, in order to respect the shape of triangular fuzzy weights, during the learning stage is proposed.

Ishibuchi proposed, using this fuzzy neural network, a classification of vectors of fuzzy numbers [2], a non-linear mapping of fuzzy numbers [3] and the approximate realisation of fuzzy if-then rules [3].

We propose an algebraic fuzzy neural network with a multilayer topology and fuzzy algebraic rules. All the operations are defined in the frame of fuzzy

arithmetic and one uses triangular fuzzy numbers (usually non-symmetric).

We develop a very simple learning algorithm based on the *trail-and-error* (TE) method. The proposed algorithm is illustrated by numerical examples.

FUZZY NEURON AND NEURAL NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

In what follows, we use only triangular fuzzy numbers, denoted by $\tilde{X} = (x^L, x^C, x^R)$.

Before describing the fuzzy neural network architecture, we briefly remember fuzzy arithmetic operations with triangular fuzzy numbers.

Let denote $\tilde{A} = (a^L, a^C, a^R)$, $\tilde{B} = (b^L, b^C, b^R)$. $\tilde{C} = (c^L, c^C, c^R)$, where \tilde{C} is $\tilde{C} = \tilde{A} \tilde{*} \tilde{B}$, and $\tilde{*}$ is a non-standard algebraic operation defined by:

$$c^L = \min\{a^L \tilde{*} b^L, a^L \tilde{*} b^C, a^L \tilde{*} b^R\} \quad (1)$$

$$c^R = \max\{a^L \tilde{*} b^L, a^L \tilde{*} b^C, a^L \tilde{*} b^R\}$$

Above, $\tilde{*} \in \{+, -, \cdot\}$ are the operations in classic arithmetic, and $\tilde{+}, \tilde{-}, \tilde{\cdot}$ are the corresponding modified operations in fuzzy arithmetics, defined according to (1).

A fuzzy neuron (Fig. 1) where all the operations are defined in fuzzy arithmetics was defined, using

the modifies extension principle (1X3) and the scheme in Figure 2.

$$\tilde{S} = \tilde{X}, \sim \tilde{W}_j + \tilde{x}_i \sim w_2 + \dots + x_r \sim w_n + \tilde{0} \quad (2)$$

$$\tilde{y} = 'K\tilde{s}' = (<Xs'), <Ks'), <p(s') \quad (3)$$

The architecture of the proposed algebraic fuzzy neural network (AFNN) is a multilayer feedforward structure (Fig. 3), using fuzzy neurons (FN), as in [4].

Fig. 1. The proposed FN

The symbols \tilde{x}_i , \tilde{w}_j and $\tilde{0}$ stand for fuzzy inputs, fuzzy weights and fuzzy biases, respectively

Fig. 2. The fuzzy activation function.

The input-output relation in the AFNN, using TFN and basic rules (1X3) is straightforward to develop and is based on the modified fuzzy arithmetic operations described above.

Fig. 3. The AFNN architecture

THE TRAIL-and-ERROR (TE) LEARNING ALGORITHM

From (1) and (2X3), it can be seen that the central values (C) of the variables operated by the AFNN are not linked to the left (L) and right values of the corresponding triangular fuzzy numbers. Hence, the C values of weights can be adapted by a classic backpropagation (BP) algorithm [5].

The L and R values are linked by *min/max* operators; a gradient algorithm is not possible, because of the nonderivability of the error function. A simple strategy can be developed to adapt the left and right values of the weights, namely *trail-and-error* (TE).

A cost function (square error term) is defined by

$$E \ll E^L + E^C + E^R \quad (4)$$

where

$$E^P = \sum_1 (d_i^P - y_i^P)^2, \quad P = L, C, R \quad (5)$$

as in classic BP [5]. In these formulas, d represents the desired values and y the actual output values of AFNN [5].

One chooses an estimate for the L, C and R weight values, in order to adapt them. This estimate Aw is obtained by BP algorithm, separately for p>= L,C,R.

First, we adapt the central (C) values of the weights. The final result is guaranteed by application of BP algorithm. Next, TE stage is applied for each L value of weight to adapt with +Aw and -Aw. One chooses the - or + sign such as the error term is the

lowest and respect the order (after adaptation) $w^{11} \dot{a}$
 $vF \dot{c} vA$. The other weights remain unchanged in
 these trials. These operations are repeated for all the
 L values of the weights.

In the same manner one adapts the R values of the
 weights. The learning algorithm can be summarised
 as follow:

- Step 0: Initialise the fuzzy weights and fuzzy biases.
- Step 1: Apply the classic BP for the central values (c indices) of weights.
- Step 2: Set the left (L) and right (R) values of weights at central values (C).
- Step 3: Forward calculation of outputs.
 Apply trail-and-error for the left (L) values of the weights.
 Forward calculation of outputs.
 Apply TE for the right (R) values of the weights.
- Step -1. Repeat by going to Step 3, until one reaches a specified stopping condition.

The fuzzy biases δ , $p = L, C, R$ are changed in the same manner.

SIMULATION RESULTS

We apply the proposed method to approximate realisation of non-linear mapping of fuzzy numbers. The TFN from input space have the bases inside the interval $[-1, 1]$ and are mapping to TFN which have the bases in $[0,+ 1]$,

In the example presented below, the AFNN has 6 inputs, 5 neurons in the hidden layer and 4 neurons in the output layer.

The learning starts with 300 iterations for adaptation of central values (C) of fuzzy weights.

The learning factor, denoted by X, is chosen 0.5. The input vector of TFN are showed in Figure 4.

The evolution of the output vector of TFN after 15 and 700 iteration is showed in Fig. 5-6.

After about 1000 iterations, the error (square root of error term E) is generally lower than 10^{-3} , a very good result. In these figures, the values below each triangle (left comer) represent the desired TFN and the right-comer values represent the actual output.

Fig. 4. The input of AFNN

Fig. 5. The output of AFNN after 15 TE iterations.

Fig. 6. The output of AFNN after 700 TE iterations.

Fig. 7. The error term evolution in the TE stage (after 300 BP iterations).

The error term evolution is shown in Fig. 7. After 300 BP iteration, the output (squared) error $E^c < 10^{-9}$, (error of 10^{-1}), as generally obtained by BP algorithm.

APPLICATION IN ECONOMICS

The algebraic fuzzy NN has an obvious utilisation in economics. Several authors have introduced some of these elements in various ways, for instance [6], [7]. The analysis of "neural-type graphs", of using fuzzy (interval type) thresholds and of logic neurons in economic applications are dealt with in [6]. Applications of neural networks and of fuzzy neural networks in economics were proposed in [8].

However, previous researches are not allowing the use of arithmetic operations with fuzzy numbers, do not really use algebraic non-linear neurons, and are not able to learn. By using true algebraic fuzzy neural networks, one can extend the models from [8] and in general the models of any fuzzy algebraic process.

Moreover, one can use algebraic fuzzy neural networks to create fuzzy algebraic models by providing to a AFNN the input and output data and letting it learn by itself the correct weights. The result after the training phase will be a AFNN that represents a *possible* model for the data. (In general, at every run of the AFNN, a new possible model is generated). In the same manner, one can correct existing models, taking the necessary number of neurons and layers, such as to appropriately

represent the structure of the processes in hand, and providing the data to the AFNN.

Furthermore, one can build by such a network a *dynamically process*, and to investigate its evolution in time, or one can optimise such processes. Examples of dynamic processes that can obviously be modelled by neural networks are given by Forester in [9].

In general, one can say that any economic process that can be described by a graph and a set of numerical (algebraic) equations can be modelled by a neural network. However, the analysis of these processes shows that only processes described by *non-linear* equations are of interest, because linear systems are better modelled by fuzzy linear combiners. Moreover, the structure of the process can impose specific constraints, for instance that some of the weights are kept to zero values. Such zero-valued weights show that there is no relation between the corresponding elements (represented by neurons, in the neural model). For instance, considering the model presented in Fig. 5.1., in [6], the permanent capitals are derived from the own capitals and from the long term exigible capitals, but not by the short term exigible capitals, i.e., the corresponding weight (connection) can have only the value 0 in the neural network.

The problem of zero valued weights can be easily solved, by imposing in the training algorithm (and software) that the starting values of these weights are zero and that they are not affected by the adaptation process.

Finally, note that a model that is well known, except the values of the coefficients, is not of interest to be modelled by a (fuzzy) neural network. Indeed, in such a case, being given a set of input and output values, one can directly solve the equations to derive the coefficients of the model. Only when the model is unknown, or there are suspicions about its validity, the use of (AF)NN is motivated.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The TE algorithm is simpler than the one proposed by Ishibuchi [2-3]. The approximation obtained in non-linear mapping of TFN is as good as the approximation obtained by the others algorithms.

The computing time, because of TE algorithm, in the case of great AFNN, may be cumbersome. One can overcome this by using an appropriate learning factor (>1.0). For the used example, with the learning factor 8.0, the training time of AFNN are comparable with the gradient algorithm proposed by Ishibuchi.

In the proposed algorithm, the symmetric triangular fuzzy numbers, as used in [2-3], are a particular case. The algorithm proposed here, based on TE, is more general and can be used for any triangular fuzzy numbers.

The AFNN described can be conveniently used to model *non-linear* economic processes. The only change is that some of the weights are kept at zero value during all the training phase of the network.

In this paper were reported some recent results in algebraic neurofuzzy systems, and in the second place the way to apply them in economic and financial analysis.

REFERENCES

- [1] H.N. Teodorescu, and Yamakawa, T. (1996): Neurofuzzy Systems: Hybrid Configurations, in print.
- [2] H. Ishibuchi, *et al* (1992): An Architecture of Neural Networks for Input Vectors of Fuzzy Numbers, Proceedings of IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems, San Diego, USA, pp. 1293-1300.
- [3] H. Ishibuchi, *et al* (1995): A learning algorithm on fuzzy neural networks with triangular fuzzy weights. Fuzzy Sets and Systems, International Journal of Soft Computing and Intelligence, IFSA, Vol. 72, No. 3, June 23, pp. 257-264
- [4] H. N. Teodorescu and Arotaritei, D. (1995): Analyses of a New Class of Algebraic Fuzzy NN, Proceedings of the International Symposium on Signals Circuits and Systems, SCS'95, Iasi, Romania, October 19-21, pp. 93-96.

[5] R. Lippman: An Introduction to Computing with Neural Nets, IEEE ASSP Magazine, pp. 4-22, (1987).

[6] A. Kaufmann, J. Gil Aluja: Técnicas de Gestión de la Empresa Ed. Pirámide, Madrid, 1992

[7] A.M. Gil Lafuente: Análisis financiero en la incertidumbre. Ariel, Barcelona 1991

[8] A. Kaufmann, J. Gil Aluja Grafts neuronales para la economía y la gestión de empresas. Pirámide, 1995

[9] J. Forester: Dinámica Industrial, El Ateneo, Buenos Aires, 1972